

MetaDocencia: A Community of Practice to Teach Teaching Open and Reproducible Research

Second Report

Note: This is not a full report. All sections with private information have been removed from this document.

Grant Overview

- Grant title: MetaDocencia: A Community of Practice to Teach Teaching Open and Reproducible Research
- Grant period: December 1, 2021 to November 30, 2024
- Date of report: February 1, 2024
- Grant purpose: To take MetaDocencia from a volunteer-based organization to a sustainable non-profit organization in the longer term.
- Project goals and milestones
 - Continue teaching technical skills for open and reproducible computational skills to Spanish-speaking researchers and instructors from Latin America and other geographies;
 - Generate new lessons and content for easy engagement for reproducibility in responsible and open science;
 - Solidify an active Latin American community of practice for open science;
 - Nurture, guide, and inspire the development of other Global-South-centered communities of practice for open and reproducible research.

I. Project Assessment

Goal 1. Continue teaching technical skills for open and reproducible computational skills to Spanish-speaking researchers and instructors from Latin America and other geographies

Deliverable 1. Organize one event every two weeks for a total of 27 events for a minimum of 15 attendees per event.

Indicators of Impact. We organized ten workshops with 141 attendees, an average of 14 attendees per event. People joined from 14 different countries, 11 of those in Latin America.

The average net promoter score (NPS), which measures whether attendants would recommend the workshop, was 96.3. NPS range is -100 to 100. Higher scores are better.

In April 2023, we co-hosted an in-person Train the Trainer two-day workshop with CABANAnet, including six attendants from Argentina and Mexico. In October 2023, we held our first hybrid workshop for 44 attendees as part of the Argentinean Biostatistics Group annual meeting.

Strengths. We completed over half of the events committed for Year 2, for almost half of the attendees expected, with a very high NPS. We have succeeded at delivering in-person and hybrid formats for the first time since MetaDocencia's inception.

Areas for Growth.

- Manage deliverable timings more efficiently. We did not complete this deliverable as initially planned because we fulfilled our longer-term sustainability during Q1 of Year 2 when NASA awarded MetaDocencia three grants to teach and develop an open science curriculum collaboratively in partnership with other projects. Attaining the sustainability milestone earlier than planned demanded extensive planning, reorganization, and a change in our plans for the rest of Year 2 for this grant. We also compensated the number of workshops committed during Year 2 by the number of conferences, events, and publications where we shared our work (see Goal 4).
- We noticed a decline in interest in our short introductory workshops, likely due to the full resumption in-person activities globally. That is why we started reorganizing our capacity-building services, diversifying their formats to in-person, hybrid, and online cohort-based over several weeks. We are also adding more topics centered around introductory, Spanish-first, open science topics.

Deliverable 2. Update of existing workshops.

Indicators of Impact. We updated and delivered new versions of our workshops "Present! Resources for Active Meetings" and "How to Teach Programming." Each workshop now has its own "compass sheet" ("hoja de ruta" in Spanish), instructor

and assistant guides, a collaborative shared document, and a Google Slide presentation. We also co-develop the contents of the 'Train the Trainer' workshop jointly with CABANAnet.

Strengths. All workshop materials remain available on MetaDocencia's website under a CC BY 4.0 license and in our Zenodo Community. We also now have templates of slides, shared documents, and other supporting material to help develop future courses. Following internal and external accessibility guidelines, we uploaded a subtitled recording of each online workshop to our YouTube channel.

Areas for Growth. In 2024, we will work on bettering our infrastructure to publish our materials in a more accessible way and with better adherence to international open science practices.

Deliverable 3. Improve event registration and certification infrastructure and procedures.

Indicators of Impact. We improved and redesigned our registration and certification process for workshops and events. The infrastructure team updated Google App Scripts that were in use and wrote new ones to automate more tasks. All scripts have been tested, documented in Spanish, and adapted to the MetaDocencia team's needs.

Strengths. This automation made our work more efficient because anyone registering for a MetaDocencia workshop or event automatically receives a confirmation email, an invitation to a Google Calendar event, and subsequent reminders. PDF attendance certificates are also generated and sent by email from a script.

Areas for Growth. We identified further opportunities to automate and optimize our registration and certification processes in the coming year. We are also exploring a badge system for certifying workshop attendants.

Goal 2. Generate new lessons and content for easy engagement and reproducibility in responsible and open science

Deliverable 1. Develop, pilot, and teach two new workshops in 2023.

Indicators of Impact.

1. The workshop "Accessible Zoom with a Screen Reader" was published and taught thrice between December 2022 and October 2023.
2. The workshop "Online Tools for Effective Teaching" was improved and piloted twice in November and December 2022.
3. The workshop "Social Impacts of Artificial Intelligence" was co-developed by MetaDocencia team members and external collaborators, who taught it in person in March 2023 during the Latin American Meeting In Artificial Intelligence (Khipu 2023) in Montevideo (Uruguay).

4. As mentioned in Goal 1, the workshop “Train the Trainers” was adapted for in-person teaching with CABANAnet team members and jointly taught to local and international participants in Buenos Aires (Argentina) in April 2023.

Strengths. Workshop 1 was very well received by the audience, especially when we connected with organizations focused on persons with visual disabilities. This workshop had requests to be translated into English, a rare event as most educational materials are usually translated from English to Spanish. Workshop 3 opened the artificial intelligence topic for us in 2023, which we maintained successfully through different publications during the year. We started exploring the intersection between AI and open science. For Workshops 3 and 4, we collaborated pedagogically with specialists from Latin America beyond our staff. Initially, they were not always part of our community, an enriching opportunity for everyone involved.

Areas for Growth. While Workshop 2 was well-received by attendees, we opted not to publish the materials as they required further revisions that we could not fulfill due to shifting the focus to our new grants. The planned workshop “How to Teach Bioinformatics” was put on hold since we have shifted our focus on this area to international collaborations towards developing joint courses and grant applications that assure our sustainability. The areas of growth noted for Goal 1 - Deliverable 1 also apply here.

Goal 3. Solidify an active Latin American community of practice for open science

Deliverable 1. Team development and growth.

Indicators of Impact.

- After a successful hiring process in mid-2022, we continued to expand our team due to increasing operational needs. We held a new hiring round for project coordination and received 134 applications during a 2-week window. We hired two persons part-time and one trainee. For this job opening, we received applications from folks coming from different backgrounds (social sciences, health sciences, engineering, natural sciences, and humanities) and from 10 Latin American countries. We also established a maternity leave policy that benefited three of our team members.
- We are a distributed team of 17 persons who work following flexible working hours, sometimes in different time zones and hemispheres. To nurture a highly functioning team, we continued with quarterly self and team 360 internal reviews that allow for constructive feedback to celebrate what works well and change what needs improvement. We also held our first in-person retreat for the whole team this year. During two days in Buenos Aires, some team members met in person for the first time.
- MetaDocencia has been committed to its internal development by protecting 10% of staff time for capacity building. We participated as mentees and mentors in OLS (cohorts 7 and 8). Team members also have the option to attend weekly English classes paid for by MetaDocencia. Several of us are regular attendees at CZI capacity-building activities such as time management, performance improvement, Community Engagement Fundamentals (with CSCCE), or

coaching sessions with BetterUp. We have also trained on collaborative lesson development with The Carpentries.

- MetaDocencia has been regularly supported by a renewed and participative Advisory Committee (AC). Our updated governance established new guidelines for the AC, and we expect to release a series of policy documents during Year 3.

Strengths. At MetaDocencia, we know that a healthy community of practice starts by having a thriving team stewarding the community. That is why we dedicate much effort and care to developing and growing our team. We have succeeded as many top players in the field recognize our staff as high, independent, and caring performers who represent MetaDocencia's values when collaborating with others. In addition, we have a thriving internal culture that facilitates going through any project. This experience positions us very well to share practical resources and advice on achieving the same with like-minded organizations.

Although run only over two weeks, our hiring process has drawn the attention of many people outside our usual network of specific communities of practice in open science and research groups, attracting increasingly talented and diverse candidates. Due to the level of care before, during, and after the process, it receives abundant positive feedback from several participants of the selection process.

MetaDocencia's team is flowing. Our first retreat and subsequent meetings in person of subteams, whenever possible, have considerably strengthened our working capacities. We are getting to know each other better, allowing us to match different staff members with the type of work where they can perform at their best.

Capacity building has a significant impact on our team. We are incredibly grateful for the CZI Movement & Capacity Building offerings.

Areas for Growth.

- To further nurture the highly talented candidates attracted by our job openings, we recently launched the Polen Project, a pilot project for selected former job applicants invited to represent MetaDocencia in events while sharing our mission, vision, and values in tailored community journeys.
- Managing a distributed team of 17 persons at most with a 0.75 FTE is a challenge. We keep improving our digital infrastructure, workflows, and organigram to perform at our best. We have underestimated the funding and time the glue and invisible work takes to manage a constantly growing and distributed team. We keep learning and working on improving our resource budgeting.

Deliverable 2. Maintain, nurture, and steward an active online community.

Indicators of Impact. Our online community has shown engagement and support throughout the past year. As of October 15, 2023,

- We increased by 88% our LinkedIn followers (from 247 to 466), by 56 % our Instagram followers (from 287 to 449), by 23% our YouTube subscribers (from 210 to 258) and Twitter followers (from 2,188 to 2,628 total), and by 10% our Facebook followers (from 1,089 to 1,200). We started building a presence in Mastodon.

- Our content had 1,345 views on YouTube, a 10% engagement rate on LinkedIn, and a 4% engagement rate on Twitter.
- MetaDocencia's website recorded 28,138 unique page views, reflecting the work we had to share with our community.
- Most of our daily communication happens via Slack. Our workspace has been growing since 2020, recording 738 members, of whom 53 joined last year, an 8% increase.
- The first seven published editions of [our newsletter](#) were well received by 2065 Spanish-speaking persons in our community (26% yearly increase) with an opening rate of 41% (2% yearly increase). On average, 487 recipients open our emails.
- [We continue to publish an English version of the newsletter to reach a wider audience.](#) The first one sent to an English-speaking audience reached 25 people, with an opening rate of 88%.

Strengths. Following a communication plan (<https://zenodo.org/records/10277837>), we produced substantial online content for social media and new content for our website. We developed the habit of sharing news, working methods, and highlighting participation in different activities. We also developed workflows to publish content openly on social media and open science platforms broadly used and recognized by our partners. We had almost 100 pieces of open material shared on our community page <https://zenodo.org/communities/metadocencia> on Zenodo by the end of 2023.

Areas for Growth. This year, due to the low number of workshops we hosted and the need to reorganize our focus our Slack activity happened mostly in closed channels within the members of our staff. Slack is not a commonly used communication platform in Latin America and often acts as a barrier. Nonetheless, with the inception of our Polen Project and more tailored community paths for our community members, together with our tutorial for the use of Slack, we are working at making our workspace more openly active.

It is onerous to maintain a presence on multiple social media platforms for a small organization such as ours. With a social network landscape in continuous change, it has been challenging to decide where to stay to still reach our audience, while sticking to our values. This is still a work in progress that will improve as we keep analyzing the data from our existing communication channels.

Deliverable 3. Collaboration with new open science communities and potential funders.

Indicators of Impact. We continued to work closely with several local and international partners. To showcase the ties we have been strengthening with other organizations on open science, community building, and education. We published a [“hive of fellow communities”](#) on our website, featuring fourteen of our partners in supporting, practicing, and nurturing open science from Latin America and beyond. We became NASA grantees and also strengthened our collaboration with Wellcome Trust.

Strengths. In the past year, we established MetaDocencia as a Latin American reference in open science education and community building (see Goal 4 -

Deliverable 1: Conference Participation). Our ability to liaise and collaborate with international partners is proven by our success in elaborating proposals and obtaining new funding (see Deliverable 4 next).

Areas for Growth. Our growth in our first 2 years as a fully funded project has been out of the charts for Latin American standards. Our team is flowing and has been adapting fast. We are still adapting to the changes and to the new challenges such growth always brings. Going from a grassroots volunteer-based organization fully based in Latin America to one of the few fully funded communities in the region working hand in hand with top agencies, universities, and funders in the open science world is a fun challenge that obliges us to revise our newly acquired standing often and rethink our strategy to fit accordingly.

Deliverable 4. Elaborate a proposal for new funding.

Indicators of Impact.

- We succeeded in co-elaborating and participating in four new funding proposals along with some of the communities in our hive of fellow communities, three of them were awarded by NASA and one by NSF.
- We are part of five preliminary proposals with different partners that are in the areas of interest of funders, such as Wellcome Trust, CZI, NASA, and [DAAD](#).

Strength. MetaDocencia is proud of the competitive funding we gathered to sustain our mission in the next three years and how we have been able to diversify our sources of income until now.

Areas for Growth. We know three years will go by fast, so we keep working on generating proposals for new funding and diversifying our income sources. We are also slowly but steadily increasing our [consulting services](#) and investigating alternative business models that will keep us true to our values.

Deliverable 5. 5-year strategic plan.

Indicators of Impact. Due to the successful revenue accrual during Years 1 and 2, elaborating a 5-year strategic plan has been delayed to Year 3. During Year 2, MetaDocencia's subteams have prepared plans to support area-specific activities and published them as tools for other communities from the region to reuse.

Areas for Growth. With 3 years of sustainability and a consolidated team, during Year 3, we will heavily calendarize yearly milestones and deliverables and make space for the elaboration of a 5-year strategic plan that will guide us during 2025-2030.

Goal 4. Nurture, guide, and inspire the development of other Global South-centered communities of practice for open and reproducible research

Deliverable 1. Conference participation.

Indicators of Impact. By the end of 2023, we have

- Participated in 20+ regional and international conferences. Several of them were invitations to talk. Our team members are already fully booked for the first semester of 2024.
- Shared information about 50+ events organized by our fellow communities in MetaDocencia's social media. Of those, 13 were media partnerships with other organizations.
- Appeared in the press. Due to a focus switch to open science and increased attention gathered through our workshops, conference participation, and new funding, several MetaDocencia team members were [interviewed](#) by different media, sharing information about our plans and views on artificial intelligence, education, and related topics.

Strengths. Receiving more invitations to conferences to present MetaDocencia's work than we can fulfill can indicate that the open science ecosystem increasingly recognizes MetaDocencia as a reference for Latin American open science education and community building. We have taken each spotlight opportunity to honor our community value as much as possible and shared the attention received as much as possible with other partners and communities to showcase themselves (e.g., csv,conf,v7 keynote presentation [talk](#)). We made every effort to make these presentations accessible in Spanish and English during the events and online through YouTube and bilingual captioning.

Areas for Growth.

- We have received more invitations than we can honor with high-quality, accessible delivery while still fulfilling the rest of our deliverables. That is another reason for creating the Polen Project, so one path in our community can be to have community members from outside the core staff team representing MetaDocencia. Whenever we cannot accept an invitation, we always try to recommend other community members for it.
- We need a more efficient pipeline for professional contextualization of Spanish-first materials into English, English-first materials into Spanish, and generating bilingual materials in general. We will be working on this pipeline during Year 3.

Deliverable 2. Improve functioning and contributors' infrastructure.

Indicators of Impact. We updated and published the scripts and tools we commonly use and prepared detailed tutorials in Spanish for each. MetaDocencia's team continued to host its webpage infrastructure on GitHub, reaching 733 commits for the website repository. We have implemented Trello for all our project management. We also modeled our multiple streams of funding using Zoho Books. Trello and Zoho Books are key pieces of internal infrastructure to follow our daily operations efficiently.

Strengths. We heavily documented all our existing infrastructure, which helped us improve it, and shared it with other organizations in Spanish.

Areas for Growth. Setting, improving, and documenting our operational infrastructure took us longer than anticipated. We share it as separate documents from a library that we keep internally in a private Google Drive that serves our

internal purposes. Nonetheless, we know there is room to keep improving our infrastructure to share our internal process and will work at improving it during Year 3.

Deliverable 3. Report our impact.

Indicators of Impact. To improve the way we measure our impact and increase the probability of contributing to the academic literature while using data responsibly (e.g., having the approval of an external Ethics Board), we started collaborating with knowledge acquisition researchers at the University of Buenos Aires, verifying the impact of our workshops on attendees. We continue to collect systematic data about our internal processes and our events through pre- and post-event surveys. Part of these data have been analyzed to prepare our presentations at different conferences and to generate our reports. Some of these publications add to the 87 open-access items in our [Zenodo community](#) between presentations, appearances in the media, blog posts, and supporting material for our workshops that are easily referenced through a DOI and a suggested citation. Some of them incorporate this grant DOI.

Strengths. One of our values is “Science and Research” to generate knowledge based on theory, reasoning, experience, and evidence. An alliance with knowledge acquisition experts at a Latin American university is a way to strengthen what we do to measure our impact effectively while managing data responsibly.

Areas for Growth. The online nature of MetaDocencia generates a wealth of data that we still have to systematize and analyze further. During Year 3, we will significantly improve our open science pipeline for analyzing all the data we gather and generate automatic reporting that can serve as a central source for all our reporting needs.

Deliverable 4. Open access publication.

Indicators of Impact.

- [Paideia Journal of Education](#) accepted a paper detailing the methods of our research project in collaboration with knowledge acquisition scholars from the University of Buenos Aires, provided we submitted some modifications, which are currently under review.
- We have also published a commissioned opinion piece about artificial intelligence and open science in English and Spanish at [Nature Human Behaviour](#). This publication will not be open-access, but the journal provided an open-access link for us to share for non-commercial use.

Strengths. Publishing in traditional academic outlets is key for projects like MetaDocencia and we successfully completed this deliverable and will continue to work in this way. We also developed the practice of publishing all of our materials on Zenodo with a CC BY 4.0 license.

Areas for Growth. Improving our impact measuring pipeline (see previous deliverable) will allow us to improve our presence in more traditional academic outlets.

II. List of Outputs Produced during Year 2

We list below 66 of the 110 outputs shared openly by MetaDocencia on our [Zenodo Community](#), three sections of our website, one academic opinion paper published in Nature Human Behaviour, one open access paper under revision, and a repository.

Among the outputs published in Zenodo are bilingual (Spanish/English) entries, including 28 educational and announcement blog posts, 16 tutorials, 9 presentations for our workshops and other events, 5 grant proposals, 3 reports, 2 templates, and 2 preparation sheets.

Output	Description/Notes
Diseño y validación del Cuestionario de Autoeficacia Docente Online	Open access paper draft under review for publication at Paideia Journal of Education
Hive of Fellow Communities (bilingual)	Website featuring some of the fellow organizations we collaborate with in Latin America and around the world
Apuntes MetaDocentes (in Spanish)	Our newsletters in Spanish
Notes from MetaDocencia	Our newsletters in English
Presentación "Estructura e infraestructura para la formación por cohortes virtuales" (in Spanish)	Presentation for the project "Structure and Infrastructure for Virtual Cohort Training", part of OLS-8.
Reporte a la comunidad 2023 (in Spanish)	2023 Report in Spanish.
Repositorio de Accesibilidad 2022-2023 (in Spanish)	Tutorial. The document includes content related to digital accessibility shared by MetaDocencia between 2022 and 2023.
Plan de infraestructura (in Spanish)	Tutorial. This infrastructure plan aims to show the development of work between 2022 and 2023, with the aim of opening our experience to the entire community and follow the philosophy of sharing knowledge and resources to foster a transparent, collaborative, and enriching environment.
Google Apps Script: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Google Apps Script platform to meet their goals.
ORCID: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the ORCID platform to meet their goals.
Slack: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the

Output	Description/Notes
	MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Slack platform to meet their goals.
Grammarly: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Grammarly tool to meet their goals.
Google Calendar: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Google Calendar platform to meet their goals.
Google Groups: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Google Groups platform to meet their goals.
Bitwarden: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Bitwarden tool to meet their goals.
Zoom: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Zoom tool to meet their goals.
Trello: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Trello platform to meet their goals.
Zenodo: instructivo (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Instructions based on the MetaDocencia experience for organizations that need to use the Zenodo platform to meet their goals.
MetaDocencia le da la bienvenida a las primeras comunidades latinoamericanas que participan en el proyecto Catalyst (in Spanish)	Blog post. In this post we share news about the Catalyst project and introduce the first Latin American communities that joined the initiative.
MetaDocencia en Slack (in Spanish)	Tutorial. In this post we share news about the use of Slack for our community.
Programa Polen - Presentación (in Spanish)	MetaDocencia's presentation for the first cohort of members of the Polen Project, where community paths will be opened to train representatives of MetaDocencia in different communities, networks, and events.

Output	Description/Notes
MetaDocencia y el enfoque comunitario hacia la ciencia y la educación abiertas (in Spanish)	Presentation shared in the talk “MetaDocencia and the community approach to open science and education” at the Knowledge Exchange Meeting 2023 organized by CABANAnet.
Cómo comunicamos 2022-2023 (in Spanish)	Tutorial. This communication plan aims to inform the planning of channels and messages for the period 2022-2023, with the objectives of increasing community size, expanding the themes of our content, and reinforcing the recognition of our identity, while promoting the participation of our community.
Cómo usamos las redes sociales (in Spanish)	Tutorial. Guidelines for the use of MetaDocencia social media profiles and suggestions for the participation of collaborators in those channels.
Latin American lessons learned on how to do outstanding global open source science	Invited presentation for AGU2023 - Panel: Voices from the Global Open Science Community: Showcasing Progress, Challenges, and Lessons Learned.
La IA generativa plantea desafíos éticos a la Ciencia Abierta, un comentario para Nature Human Behaviour (in Spanish)	Blog post in Spanish presenting our latest academic publication, authored with colleagues from the University of the Republic of Uruguay, on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Open Science.
Generative AI poses ethical challenges to Open Science. a comment for Nature Human Behaviour	Blog post in English presenting our latest academic publication, authored with colleagues from the University of the Republic of Uruguay, on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Open Science.
Generative AI poses ethical challenges to Open Science (open access link provided to authors for dissemination, bilingual)	Paper in English in Nature Human Behaviour
Espacios de crecimiento para aprender a dar y recibir devoluciones positivas (in Spanish)	Blog post. Aware of the importance of holding spaces that nurture personal and collective growth and development, in 2022 MetaDocencia created the "MEC survey", an acronym derived from "MetaDocencia: Espacios de Crecimiento" ("MetaDocencia: Spaces for Growth"). Spanish version.
Spaces for Growth: Learning How to Give and Receive Positive Feedback	Blog post. Aware of the importance of holding spaces that nurture personal and collective growth and development, in 2022 MetaDocencia created the "MEC survey", an

Output	Description/Notes
	acronym derived from "MetaDocencia: Espacios de Crecimiento" ("MetaDocencia: Spaces for Growth"). English version.
Keynote Co-Afina 2023 "MetaDocencia: Co-creando y enseñando Ciencia Abierta en comunidad" (in Spanish)	Presentation for the keynote talk at Co-Afina 2023 "MetaDocencia: Co-creando y enseñando Ciencia Abierta en comunidad"
Guía para la participación en el espacio de Slack de MetaDocencia (in Spanish)	Tutorial. This guide to participation in the MetaDocencia Slack space includes guidelines and suggestions for profile configuration, sharing content, and conversation.
The team gets bigger!	Blog post. In September, three people joined the team (yes, 3!) after an open call for a project coordinator. English version.
¡Se agranda el equipo! (in Spanish)	Blog post. In September, three people joined the team (yes, 3!) after an open call for a project coordinator. Spanish version.
Open grant narrative: A Collaborative Interactive Computing Service Model for Global Communities MetaDocencia	Grant. We recently submitted a grant to Chan Zuckerberg Initiative and wish to share some details about it as well as the grant narrative for others to read and re-use.
Narrativa abierta de financiamiento: Modelo de servicio computacional interactivo y colaborativo para comunidades globales (in Spanish)	Blog post announcing in Spanish the narrative of a collaborative service model above.
Nuevo proyecto: Infraestructura en la nube y entrenamiento en ciencia abierta para comunidades de América Latina y África (in Spanish)	Cross-posted blog post between MetaDocencia (in Spanish), 2i2c (in English), and IOI (in English). The proposal for this project was approved for funding by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative.
Presentación Curso ¡Presente! Recursos para Encuentros Activos (in Spanish)	Presentation of the "Present! Resources for Active Meetings" workshop prepared for the Argentine Biostatistics Group (GAB) annual scientific meeting.
MetaDocencia apoya el desarrollo del Centro C3 de Arecibo, financiado por NSF (in Spanish)	Blog post. MetaDocencia will be part of the Arecibo C3 project, a new research and education center with a focus on equity and inclusion, with the support of the United States National Science Foundation.
Uniando comunidades para ampliar la participación en la Ciencia Abierta (in Spanish)	Blog post. OLS, MetaDocencia, and other international organizations are proud to announce their collaboration to develop the

Output	Description/Notes
	Open Seeds OLS-8 program.
Open Science Accesible: Teaching TOPS OpenCore in English	Grant. Proposal for the NASA-TOPST award titled “Open Science Accesible: Teaching TOPS OpenCore in English”.
We started to transform toward Open Science together with NASA: 10 points!	Blog post. With OLS, 2i2c, and the support of NASA, we join the initiative to transform science and technology to open practices. How did we get here? What does it represent? How will we work? What reach and impact do we expect? We tell you more in this blog post. English version.
Arrancamos a transformarnos hacia la Ciencia Abierta junto con la NASA: ¡10 puntos! (in Spanish)	Blog post. With OLS, 2i2c, and the support of NASA, we join the initiative to transform science and technology to open practices. How did we get here? What does it represent? How will we work? What reach and impact do we expect? We tell you more in this blog post. Spanish version.
Ciencia Abierta Accesible: Teaching TOPS OpenCore in Spanish	Grant. Statement of Work Update for the NASA-TOPST grant proposal “Ciencia Abierta Accesible: Community-Based Teaching of the TOPS OpenCore Online in Spanish”.
Reproducibly Analyzing Wildfire, Drought, and Flood Risk with NASA Earthdata Cloud	Grant. This document is a proposal from 2i2c and MetaDocencia (both are fiscally sponsored projects of Code for Science & Society) to the NASA SMD call for proposals F.14 Transform to Open Science Training (NNH22ZDA001N-TOPST). This was one of 16 successfully funded proposals under the program.
CW23: las comunidades de práctica y la aspiración a una Ciencia Abierta a escala global (in Spanish)	Blog post. As part of the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) Collaborations Workshop (CW23), LA-CoNGA physics and MetaDocencia, with the support of The Turing Way, organized a hybrid workshop around the universality of current Open Science concepts and practices.
Artificial Intelligence and Education: More Questions Than Answers	In this blog post , we share some critical thoughts and ideas about the potential uses of AI in Education.
Thinking Critically about Artificial Intelligence and Education	In this blog post , we share some critical thoughts and ideas about the potential uses of AI in Education.

Output	Description/Notes
Inteligencia Artificial y Educación: Más preguntas que respuestas (in Spanish)	In this blog post we share many questions that we recommend asking yourself when you see the rise of Artificial Intelligence applied to Education.
Inteligencia Artificial y Educación: Reflexiones críticas (in Spanish)	In this blog post we share many questions that we recommend asking yourself when you see the rise of Artificial Intelligence applied to Education.
Plantilla para el armado de presentaciones MetaDocencia (in Spanish)	Template for preparing presentations for MetaDocencia with the organization's aesthetics and resources.
Plantilla para el armado de presentaciones de cursos MetaDocencia (in Spanish)	Template for preparing presentations for MetaDocencia's workshops with the organization's aesthetics and resources.
How in-class assessments can improve learning	Blog post. Assessments not only measure knowledge, they also help strengthen it. In this article, we share tips for implementing formative assessments. English version.
Cómo las evaluaciones durante la clase pueden mejorar el aprendizaje (in Spanish)	Blog post. Assessments not only measure knowledge, they also help strengthen it. In this article, we share tips for implementing formative assessments. Spanish version.
Comunidades de práctica y su influencia en la difusión de la ciencia abierta en Latinoamérica (in Spanish)	Blog post. We wonder what the role of communities of practice is in the dissemination and implementation of open science practices in general, and specifically, in the Latin American region.
Some How-Tos for Building and Supporting Open Source Science Communities in Africa and Latin America	In this blog post we focus on short-, medium- and long-term actions that funders, researchers, and others can take to remove some of the barriers to participation, based on the contributions of the panelists and moderators of a Turing Way Fireside Chat. English version.
Acciones para crear y apoyar comunidades científicas de código abierto en África y América Latina (in Spanish)	In this blog post we focus on short-, medium- and long-term actions that funders, researchers, and others can take to remove some of the barriers to participation, based on the contributions of the panelists and moderators of a Turing Way Fireside Chat. Spanish version.
¿Cómo nació MetaDocencia? (in Spanish)	Blog post. Laura Ación shares the milestones that led to MetaDocencia in the article

Output	Description/Notes
	MetaDocencia: Teaching to Teach (Bioinformatics and more) Online in Spanish , published on January 13, 2021.
Collective Creation of Open Science / Creación Colectiva de Ciencia Abierta	Keynote presentation at csv.conf 2023. Communities of practice are key to develop and adopt Open Science, particularly in the Global South.
Curso How to teach programming online (in Spanish)	Preparation sheet for the workshop, whose objective is to introduce techniques and good practices to design programming courses and evaluate students. English version.
Curso Cómo enseñar a programar online (in Spanish)	Preparation sheet for the workshop, whose objective is to introduce techniques and good practices to design programming courses and evaluate students. Spanish version.
2022 Report. A Year of Changes and Growth.	In this report we share our year of changes, growth, consolidation, and learning, along with resources for the entire community. English version.
Reporte 2022. Un año de cambios y crecimiento. (in Spanish)	In this report we share our year of changes, growth, consolidation, and learning, along with resources for the entire community. Spanish version.
Inteligencia artificial y políticas públicas (in Spanish)	Presentation on Artificial Intelligence and Public Policy within the cycle "Artificial Intelligence: The frontiers of the possible" organized by the Center for Public Studies, Chile.
Buenas prácticas para crear presentaciones accesibles (in Spanish)	Blog post reviewing a series of suggestions to help allow presentations to be used by a greater number of people.
¿Cómo organizar las pestañas y ventanas para dar una clase virtual sincrónica? (in Spanish)	In this blog post , we recommend one of the possible ways to organize the windows on your screen to keep all online course attendees within sight.
2023 SSI Fellowship Application - EspañOLS: empowering Open Science ambassadors in Spanish-speaking communities	Presentation used to apply for the 2023 Software Sustainability Institute fellowship program.
MetaDocencia's Governance	Blog post. This document is the result of a collaborative process for the development of MetaDocencia's governance and decision-making. English version.

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Gobernanza de MetaDocencia (in Spanish)	Blog post. This document is the result of a collaborative process for the development of MetaDocencia's governance and decision-making. Spanish version.
MetaDocencia: A Community of Practice to Teach Teaching Open and Reproducible Research	Grant. Redacted MetaDocencia Proposal for CZI with the goal of taking MetaDocencia from a volunteer-based organization to a long-term sustainable nonprofit.
Google Scripts for Workshop Registration Automation (in Spanish)	Repository sharing scripts for automating some of the processes for our workshops